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NET-Fuels D1.2 DMP-V3.0

NET-Fuels DMP Version V3.0, Update period M19-M36

Dissemination Level: Public

NET- Fuels | INCREASING BIOMASS CONVERSION EFFICIENCY TO CARBON-NEGATIVE SUSTAINABLE BIOFUELS BY COMBINATION OF THERMOCHEMICAL AND BIO-ELECTROCHEMICAL PROCESSES

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NET-Fuels consortium

Short	Beneficiary	Role
UNIBO	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	CO
FRA	Fraunhofer UMSICHT	BEN
LEITAT	Acondicionamiento Tarrasense (LEITAT)	BEN
SUT	Silesian University of Technology	BEN
ITHAKA	Ithaka Institute	BEN
REACH	REACH Innovation	BEN
WRG	WRG Europe	AP

CO...Coordinator, BEN...Beneficiary, AP...Associated Partner

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Abbreviations

CC – Creative Commons
DMO - Data Management Officer
DMP - Data Management Plan
DOI – Digital Object Identifier
EC – European Commission
FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable & Reusable
MX – Project Month X
PID – Persistent Identifier
RDM – Research Data Management
RP – Reporting Period
WP – Work Package

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Executive Summary

NET-Fuels is a publicly funded Horizon Europe project and as such is committed to following good practices of efficient and transparent data management as well as to implement the Open Science and Open Data mandate of the European Commission (EC).

The Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the handling of data throughout the NET-Fuels project and by that it serves to ensure transparency and efficient cooperation within the project, thus guaranteeing a high-quality project implementation. Further, it provides orientation to the project partners as well as to third parties, such as researchers, policy-makers and other stakeholders, regarding the content, validity and accessibility of the project's data and other outputs.

The management of the NET-Fuels data aspires to respond to the specific needs of the project partners as well as to preserve their best practices in data handling, to harmonize them among the partners, and to integrate them with the requirements of good scientific practice as well as to those of the funding institution. It was thus co-created by the partners under the lead of REACH, within WP1 Task T1.3.

For research data and other outputs that are potentially useful to third parties, the Horizon Europe Open Science rules are applied, which serve to encourage and facilitate the validation as well as the reuse of the project results. The FAIR principles will be implemented for research data (data should be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable), but the consortium will also comply with those principles regarding any other kinds of outputs whenever it is to be expected that third parties benefit from them.

This document contains an overview of the types of data and other outputs that are expected to result from the NET-Fuels project action, as well as the data management strategy adopted in this project. It further includes a detailed overview over the expected datasets and their respective handling procedures. In the Annex, a template of the dataset tables and the instructions that were provided to the partners can be found.

D1.2 - DMP V3.0 is a revised data management plan, for the period of M19-M36 of the project, which incorporates changes. considered appropriate by the WPs Tasks' leaders, on the Data Tables of the WPs Tasks, in relation to the information provided in the previously updated version of the DMP.

The current document is the third of four planned DMP versions for NET-Fuels. The submitted versions are: the DMP Version 1.0, published on April 2023; the DMP Version 2.0, published on June 2024; and the current DMP Version 3.0, made available on January 2026, covering updates of the period of July 2024 to December 2025. The next and last version of the DMP (Version 4.0) will be published on the closing month of project development (M48), October 2026.

1 Introduction & Background

NET-Fuels is a publicly funded Horizon Europe project and as such is committed to following good practices of efficient and transparent data management as well as to implement the Open Science and Open Data mandate of the European Commission (EC) (see esp. Article 17 Model Grant Agreement). This data management plan (DMP) outlines the handling of data throughout the NET-Fuels project in accordance with these commitments.

The DMP serves to ensure transparency and efficient cooperation within the project, thus guaranteeing the high quality of the project implementation. Further, it provides orientation to third parties regarding the content, validity and accessibility of the project's data and other outputs.

The current document is the third (DMP V3.0) of four planned DMP versions. As data management concerns the entire data life cycle, details regarding the handling of data will become clear and/or change over time. For this reason, the DMP is considered a living document and will be updated in accordance with the concrete development of the project and will become more detailed over time.

1.1 Objectives and Approach

The development of a data management strategy and the DMP as its main output is part of the project's WP1 task T1.3. It especially serves the objective of coordinating the scientific, technological and administrative efforts of the various partners.

The main objectives of the NET-Fuels DMP are to:

- Identify data types and dataset formats for all data that is created or collected.
- Cover standards and methodologies for data collection and management, as well as ethics and IP restrictions.
- Ensure data sharing and access plans.
- Define a long-term data preservation strategy for the project data.

The approach taken by REACH for the development of the NEW-Fuels DMP was based on the specific needs of the partners, while at the same time providing guidance to them to observe the pertinent rules.

The methodologies and standards that apply to the NET-Fuels data handling differ depending on the respective types of data. The three types of data and their respective handling rules addressed in this DMP are:

1. **Research Data**,
2. **Other Outputs** (such as deliverables, publications, or software), and
3. **Supporting Data** (such as project management data and all kinds of preparatory data, which includes all research data or other outputs before their finalization).

In this document, the term "data" is used as an umbrella term for these three types of data in the broad sense. When referring to a specific type of data, it will be stated explicitly.

Figure 1: Types of NET-Fuels Data.

In this DMP, primary focus is given to the research data that is collected and generated in connection with the project action. However, also other outputs that are potentially useful to third party researchers and the general public are addressed. The handling of publications is not addressed in depth in this DMP, as this topic is addressed by the Dissemination and Exploitation tasks of the project, with its preliminary plan disseminated within D6.2 [16], updated within D6.3 [17]. Nevertheless, section 3.3 of this document addresses how publications are linked to the research data on which they are based. Finally, also the general principles of the handling of all supporting project data are briefly outlined.

All project data are subject to established standards and methodologies concerning the good practice handling of data.¹ By applying those rules and principles to the specific datasets generated by the project, this DMP constitutes a tailor-made strategy that is responsive to the needs of the partners, while at the same time ensuring the quality and efficiency of the project.

In addition, for research data and other outputs that are potentially useful to third parties, the Horizon Europe Open Science rules² are applied, which serve to encourage and facilitate the validation as well as the reuse of the project results. In this context, especially the FAIR principles³ are of utmost importance. Their fulfilment is mandatory for research data. NET-Fuels Consortium also complies with those principles regarding any other kinds of outputs, whenever it is expected that the public may benefit from them.

1.2 Key Audiences

The audience of this DMP is plural. Primarily, the DMP serves to harmonize the data management procedures of the individual project partners, as well as to enforce best practices of data management throughout the consortium. Hence, it is an important point of reference for the partners during the project implementation.

Secondly, third party researchers that work in the field of biofuels or on topics related to any of the individual task outcomes (e.g.: material researchers, renewable energy researchers, simulation and model developers, technical constructors etc.) benefit from this DMP as it provides them with a map and instructions for finding and reusing the project's data. It will allow them to know where they can find which kind of the project's data and outputs and at which point in time and how the data is connected to the final results, most importantly the publications resulting from the project, allowing them to verify the validity.

¹ For a collection of best practices, see e.g. <https://www.axiomdatascience.com/best-practices/index.html#>

² https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf, esp. pp 37ff.

Thirdly, third party researchers and data managers can benefit from the established good practices, procedures and materials contained in this DMP and are, in fact, explicitly encouraged to reuse the DMP or its parts for their own projects, under the conditions of the CC-BY license.

Fourthly, various stakeholders of the biofuels market such as end-users, industry or public entities benefit from consulting this DMP as it enables them to quickly grasp the timeline, location of the project results and of the institutions involved in the development of the individual results.

Finally, this DMP also serves to enable the project reviewers to evaluate the compliance of this project's data management procedures with the relevant requirements.

1.3 Structure

The structure of this DMP is as follows: Section 2 gives a brief overview of the types of data and other outputs that are expected to result from the NET-Fuels project action. Section 3 explains in detail the data management strategy adopted in this project, through which the objectives outlined in the previous section are to be implemented. Section 4 presents the data tables related to each NET-Fuels work package task, providing details about the expected datasets and their respective handling procedures. Especially section 4 is expected to be subject to the most revision over time, as not all datasets can be foreseen at the point of the first version of the DMP. Section 5 draws pertinent conclusions concerning the main part of the DMP. Finally, the Annex contains a template of the dataset tables and the instructions that were provided by REACH to the partners for the data tables completion.

2 Summary of NET-Fuels Data

NET-Fuels will collect and generate data on a wide range of topics related to the project action.

The NET-Fuels Main Project Action aims at:

- **Developing a novel pathway to produce carbon-negative biofuels** from low value biogenic residues (such as digestate, calamity wood, pruning),
- through a combination of thermochemical conversion, separation of hydrogen from the syngas, oxy-fuel combustion of the tail gas, bio-electrochemical conversion of CO₂ into methane and carbon sequestration in the biochar, which
- generate as an additional product a biofuel intermediary (high quality pyrolysis oil).

The project action is divided into six work packages, each divided into several specific tasks. From each task, potentially research data and other outputs (models, software or training and information material) will emerge.

Figure 2: PERT diagram of NET-Fuels Project with its Work Packages.

NET-Fuels work plan is then composed of the following work packages (WPs): WP1 Management, coordination and risk management, led by UNIBO; WP2 Thermo-chemical conversion of biogenic residues and supply of CO₂ and biochar, led by FRA; WP3 Bioelectrochemical process for CO₂ conversion to CH₄ from off-gas streams, led by LEITAT; WP4 Sustainability and carbon sink assessment, led by UNIBO; WP5 Business Development and Potential Industrial Scale-up, led by REACH; and WP6 Dissemination, exploitation, and communication, led by partner WRG. WP leaders will coordinate the work and oversee the execution and progress of the Tasks within each WP, being also responsible for the quality check of the WPs' outputs.

The project’s deliverables, which in most cases contain project-specific processing of the research data, are considered as the most important type of other outputs. The supporting data includes all those data that do not fall into the group of research data or other outputs. Notable supporting data are the project management data, as well as any kind of data that is necessary for the finalization of research data and other outputs.

The main sets of data and other outputs generated and collected throughout the WPs are listed in the following table. As all tasks will generate supporting data, they will not be mentioned in the table below. With the progression of the project implementation, more sets of research data and other outputs are expected to be identified and will accordingly be added to this table.

Table 1: NET-Fuels Data per Work Package

Work Packages	Research Data	Other Outputs
WP1 Management, coordination and risk management	N/A	<i>D1.1 - Project management plan. D1.2 - Data management plan.</i>
WP2 Thermo-chemical conversion of biogenic residues and supply of CO₂ and biochar	Data on feedstock assessment (digestate, calamity wood, prunings). Simulation data of TCR heat transfer and oxy-combustion. Data on gas analysis of CO ₂ stream from oxyfuel combustion. Energy and mass balance assessing the performance of the TCR pilot plant with pyrolysis, hydrogen separation and oxyfuel combustion. Biochar physical properties, data on biochar agronomic tests (yield and other plant parameters w/o and w/ biochar).	Model of TCR heat transfer and oxy-combustion.
		<i>D2.1 - Report on feedstock characterisation. D2.2 - Report on CFD model and simulations on oxyfuel combustion and heat transfer. D2.3 - Report on plant operation performance with mass and energy balance. D2.4 - Report on field trials of the biochar.</i>
WP3 Bio-electrochemical process for CO₂ conversion to CH₄ from off-gas streams	BEM reactor simulation data. BEM reactor piloting data. BEM reactor operation and validation data (Methane Analysis, Mass Energy balance).	BEM reactor design.
		<i>D3.1 - Report on construction, performance and optimization of BEM reactors. D3.2 - Report on design, construction and operation of BEM pilot plant.</i>
WP4 Sustainability and carbon sink assessment	Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) and Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA). Data on NET-Fuels Life Cycle Analysis for different scenarios.	Framework on sustainability assessment. Parametric model building to compute GHGs emissions.

	<p>qualitative data of cultural and political dimensions. Data on carbon sink assessment.</p>	<p><i>D4.1 - Methodologies for the sustainability analysis of the NET-Fuels technology.</i> <i>D4.2 - NET-Fuels LCIA interpretation.</i> <i>D4.3 - NET-Fuels dynamic environmental impact assessment and GHG emission calculation.</i> <i>D4.4 - Socio-economic effects of the adoption of NET-Fuels.</i> <i>D4.5 - Guideline for the Carbon sink assessment for NET-Fuels production.</i></p>
<p>WP5 Business Development and Potential Industrial Scale-up</p>	<p>Technology Market Research Analysis. Data on NET-Fuels market and competitive technologies.</p> <p>Business Models for NET-Fuels Exploitable Results.</p> <p>Business Cases defined for different technologies configurations of the NET-Fuels proposed overall system, and Roadmap for the project’s Business Plan.</p>	<p>Technology Watch database. SWOT analysis comparison data. Techno-economic model for industrial scale-up.</p> <p><i>D5.1 - NET-Fuels Market and Competitive Research Analysis.</i> <i>D5.2 - NET-Fuels Business Model & Business Plan Development.</i> <i>D5.3 - NET-Fuels Technology Regulatory Assessment.</i> <i>D5.4 - Scale-up of the integrated NET-Fuels technology system for industrial level.</i></p>
<p>WP6 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication</p>	<p>Intellectual Property Analysis for NET-Fuels Key-Exploitable Results.</p> <p>Roadmap for NET-Fuels Exploitation beyond the project lifetime.</p>	<p>Communication materials. Website signup data. News and blogs. Dissemination activity-logs. Exploitation activity-logs. Exploitation Check-book.</p> <p><i>D6.1 - Website and project branding.</i> <i>D6.2 - Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan.</i> <i>D6.3 - First dissemination, exploitation and communication report.</i> <i>D6.4 - Second dissemination, exploitation, and communication report.</i></p>

Most of NET-Fuels deliverables will be available publicly. Which deliverables will be public and where they can be found is outlined in the data tables in section 4. The time schedule of the completion of the deliverables is outlined in the figure below.

A more detailed account of the individual datasets that includes their dissemination status, timeline and storage location is given in section 4 of this document.

3 NET-Fuels Data Management Strategy

The management of the NET-Fuels data aspires to respond to the specific needs of the project partners as well as to preserve their well-established and tried data handling practices, to harmonize them among the partners, and to integrate them with the requirements of good scientific practice as well as to those of the funding institution. To meet these various demands, a customized data management strategy has been devised for the project, led by REACH, in continuous consultation with all project partners.

For the purpose of identifying and assessing the current data handling practices and data needs of the individual institutions, REACH has distributed in M3 data tables on a WP-task basis (see Annex) to the partners. Further, in M4, a workshop dedicated to answering open questions regarding the data tables and further harmonizing the NET-Fuels project data management procedures was organized by REACH. The filled-out data tables were returned to REACH by M5. Then REACH defined the appropriate common strategy in the form of this DMP. Abridged versions of the partner's filled-out data tables can be found in section 4 of this document. D1.2 DMP V3.0 updates those data tables, in relation to the ones published in D1.2 DMP V1.0 and updated as D1.2 DMP V2.0 [20], according to the feedback received from the WPs Tasks Leaders for the current DMP update.

In this section, firstly, the responsibilities of the partners and individual team members regarding data management will be laid out. Secondly, the storage infrastructure including the topics of safety and handling procedures will be outlined. Thirdly, the special data handling procedures that are necessary for satisfying the FAIR principles are addressed.

3.1 Responsibilities and Communication

As task leader, REACH carries the main responsibility for the definition and implementation control of the data management strategy. Accordingly, this DMP is developed by REACH, with input from all consortium partners as specialists of their specific data.

The implementation of the data management strategy is the responsibility of all project partners. To facilitate efficient communication between REACH and the teams of the individual tasks, each partner institution has appointed a Data Management Officer (DMO). The DMO is a partner member and can be, but is not necessarily, also the person that is the task leader. From the perspective of the individual task, task leader and DMO are always from the same institution. See illustration on Figure 4.

Figure 4: NET-Fuels Data Management Officer Strategy.

The responsibility of the DMO is to support the task contributors in which his/her institution is the task leader regarding the handling of the data in the specific task. Further, the DMO is also responsible for continuously Whenever the DMO is in doubt about an aspect of data management regarding a specific task, he/she can contact REACH for advice. In turn, for the purpose of implementation control, REACH contacts the DMO whenever issues of proper implementation of the data management strategy arise. The DMOs, defined for each partner and communicated within the project consortium form the communicative bridge between REACH and the individual task contributors, i.e. most importantly the respective task leaders, but also the individual task's team members. For this update of DMP V3.0, the DMO partner members have been revised and updated in M36. For the sake of data protection, their names are not listed in this public document.

3.2 Storage Infrastructure

The storage concept of the NET-Fuels project is devised to facilitate collaboration among the partners, while at the same time maintaining the well-established and tried data storage practices of the individual partners. A further concern is the fulfilment of safety, transparency and the FAIR principles.

To meet these diverse demands, data will not be stored centrally, but distributed to several different locations, depending on its nature and purpose. To ensure transparency and to prevent data loss despite the decentralized storage infrastructure, clear rules and procedures regarding storage practices are necessary.

In the following, the different types of repositories including their respective characteristics and purpose in the project will be outlined. Then, rules to ensure the uniform handling of all data throughout the consortium partners will be laid out.

3.2.1 Repositories

The decentralized storage infrastructure consists of several types of repositories, each responding to a different sharing and storage need:

1. **Institutional repositories** are used for the storage of each partner's research data and other outputs and all of its supporting data. The **institutional repositories are managed by the respective partners** and fulfil the state-of-the-art safety requirements, aligned with [4] [12].
2. Data that takes the form of documents (i.e. **not research data**) that needs to be shared among the consortium internally, will be stored on a **SharePoint repository** managed by UNIBO for the duration of the project.
3. **Data that will be made public**, will be stored on a **repository classified as "trusted"** according to the criteria of the EC [14].⁴ The partners are free to choose repositories that fulfil this condition. However, NET-Fuels Consortium has decided to use the general-purpose open repository Zenodo⁵, set-up and maintained by REACH, to store the public research data and document of the project [18].

The characteristics and purpose of each type of repository used for NET-Fuels are defined as illustrated in Table 2.

⁴ <https://www.openaire.eu/find-trustworthy-data-repository>

⁵ For an overview of how Zenodo fulfils the criteria of a trusted repository see here: <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>.

Table 2: Use of NET-Fuels Repositories and their Characteristics.

NET-Fuels Repositories and their Characteristics					
Repositories	Data Types	Access	Backup	Archiving	Costs
Institutional Repositories (managed by the partner's institutions)	Supporting and finalized data	Generally accessible to the individual partner only, however individual datasets are made available by the respective partner to other consortium members based on need.	At least weekly	Yes	Covered by overhead project budget
Project SharePoint (managed by UNIBO)	Project management data, supporting and finalized <u>documents</u> , such as deliverables. NOT: Research data	All files are available to all partners via a secure login procedure	At least weekly	No	Covered by overhead project budget
Trusted Open Access Repositories (Zenodo⁶ by default)	All research data that is not subject to an embargo; all outputs that are of interest to third parties ⁷	Publicly and freely accessible ⁸	Yes	Yes	Free of charge

Due to this storage infrastructure strategy, all project data has a determinate storage location, including a clear allocation of responsibility for its safety and long-term preservation. Some data will be available in several storage locations at the same time.

3.2.2 Data Handling Procedures

To ensure the efficient and transparent exchange of data, the consortium has agreed to follow certain data handling procedures.

- **File Storage Structure**

In the project SharePoint, the partners will follow a uniform file storage structure. Each WP has been assigned an individual folder. Within these WP folders, further folders for the individual WP-tasks are available. Within these WP-Tasks folders, there are folders for the tasks' deliverables. The further file structure is to be defined by the partners according to their needs, in a way that facilitates intuitive navigation and transparency throughout the folders. The partners are advised to adopt similar structures on their individual institutional repositories.

- **Naming Conventions**

⁶ NET-Fuels Zenodo Community: https://zenodo.org/communities/net_fuels_horizon_europe_project/.

⁷ To see which ones those outputs are, see the individual task tables in section 4.

⁸ For details see section 3.3 .

Throughout all storage locations the partners will follow concise naming conventions. Each file needs to reference the WP-task, the authoring partner(s), its version and a descriptive title of the content of the file (e.g. WP1-T1.3_REACH_DataTable_Guide_V1.0.pdf).

- **Transparency Mechanisms**

Further, all partners commit to transparency mechanisms in the handling of data. They inform each other about the finalization, upload and deletion of data that is of common concern to all partners. In the SharePoint, the partners have the possibility to enable notifications whenever documents are uploaded or edited. Whenever necessary, the partners upload data documentation files to ensure quick orientation within the datasets.

3.3 Satisfying the FAIR Principle

As the main pillar of the Open Science mandate, all results, such as publications, data and other outputs should be made accessible to the public to the greatest extent possible [4] [12]. The FAIR Principle sets out the criteria how this is to be realized [6].^{9,10}

The FAIR Principle requires Data to be:

Findable, Accessible, Interoperable & Reusable

In Horizon Europe projects, the FAIR Principle applies mandatorily to research data and is strongly recommended also for other outputs. The current document outlines how the FAIR principle is satisfied by the NET-Fuels data management strategy regarding research data and other outputs.

The data tables provided to the partners for the purpose of defining the NET-Fuels data management strategy (see Annex) was modelled primarily after the Horizon Europe DMP template.¹¹ Accordingly, the data table covers topics such as the dissemination classification of the data (private, consortium or public). Further, the topic of dataset specific metadata, disciplinary data handling standards, sharing timeline, persistent identifiers, file formatting, ownership and licensing, ethical issues and archiving and preservation were queried. The answers from the partners were adjusted by REACH, so as to meet the FAIR principles.

The partners were instructed to justify thoroughly whenever open access cannot be granted, making clear which permissible reasons allow to do so. Further, the consortium is aware that also closed data can be FAIR (in the sense that the data is made *'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'*). This is achieved in this project by registering the existence of the data in a trusted repository, despite not making the content (fully) accessible.

In this section, some aspects of the FAIR principle that concerns all NET-Fuels datasets are outlined in the sequel. Section 4 then contains the datasets referring to research data and/or other outputs of the project's WPs with specificities regarding their handling.

⁹ Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management from "Science Europe, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915862>.

¹⁰ HE Programme Guide, https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf, pp 37ff.

¹¹ <https://enspire.science/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Horizon-Europe-Data-Management-Plan-Template.pdf>

3.3.1 Metadata

For all datasets, common keywords were defined, which are to be used as metadata for all public datasets. Below you find a list of used keywords to be further extended by the partners:

1. Horizon Europe
2. NET-Fuels
3. Grant Number: 101083780
4. Advanced Biofuels
5. Biochar
6. Bio-Electrochemical Methanation
7. Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU)
8. Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS)
9. Pyrolysis
10. Oxy-fuel Combustion
11. Synthetic Methane
12. Green Hydrogen
13. etc.

In addition to these general metadata keywords, the individual datasets will add task-related specific keywords to the metadata (see data tables in section 4).

In addition to keywords, metadata for all datasets will also include documentation as well as an indication of the type of CC licence that is assigned to the document.

Consortium partners will only use trusted repositories, so that the interoperability of the metadata is ensured.¹²

3.3.2 Sharing

Unless classified as closed due to IP protection or sensitivity of data, all research data and other outputs will be made public upon their completion (in the latter case, only provided it is of use to third parties). In case scientific publications result from any part of the project action, supporting data will be published at the latest at the time the publication is released.

The research data is to be made public in its raw form, and only curation that is necessary for the intelligibility of the data is performed by the researchers. The task leaders, supported by the respective DMO, are responsible for the adequate curation and sharing of the research data in a trusted repository. The fulfilment of this duty will be monitored by partner REACH through its DMO and the team involved in WP1-T1.3.

The procedure for the publication of the deliverables is also encouraged to be done by the authoring partners upon completion if not explicitly specified otherwise in the individual data tables in section 4. In case the authoring partners do not upload the deliverables, REACH will take over the responsibility and will publish them on Zenodo, linked to the [NET-Fuels Zenodo Community](#).

All public data will be linked with each other. This means that all data supporting a publication will reference in its metadata, as well as in the dataset itself the PID (persistent identifier) of the publication, and vice versa. All other outputs will equally be linked to the project's other results, and vice versa. Further, the NET-Fuels website (<https://www.netfuelsproject.org/>) has a dedicated section in which all public datasets will be linked in a structured manner, referring to the open repository of the project, aligned with [7].

¹² See e.g. for Zenodo: <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>

The consortium will use the Creative Commons (CC) Licence 4.0¹³ framework [8] for the purpose of making research data and other outputs available for further use to the public. Either CC-BY or CC0 licences will be applied to research data. Whenever possible, other outputs will also receive CC0 or CC-BY licence, but at times a more restrictive licence may be necessary for protecting the interest of the consortium. Metadata will always receive a CC0 licence. Check Figure 5 below for details concerning the CC0 and CC-BY licences, as well as Figure 6 for the explanation of all Creative Commons Licences.

Figure 5: Overview about CC0 and CC-BY Creative Commons licences¹⁴

Figure 6: Creative Commons Licences explanation¹⁵

¹³ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>

¹⁴ "Overview of the six main Creative Commons licenses and CC0" by "Floba007" is licensed under CC BY 4.0, cropped.

¹⁵ "Creative Commons Licences explanation", adapted from [Creative Commons Licences](#), Foter.com, licensed under CC BY-SA 2.0, cropped.

3.3.3 Long-Term Preservation

The originals of all research datasets and other outputs are stored in the institutional repositories of the respective authoring partners for at least 2-5 years after project completion. A copy of all public datasets will be stored in a trusted repository, which provides indefinite long-term storage. In that way, all data will be stored at least in one location (in the case of sensitive data only on the institutional repository), and in most cases in two locations simultaneously (public data institutional repositories and public trusted repositories).

Whenever the conditions for a dataset being closed fall away, the partners will make them available on a trusted repository, and that so, even if this occurs only after project completion.

The project's SharePoint will not be available to the partners after project completion. Project Consortium Partners are thus advised to make copies of the SharePoint's relevant contents to their institutional repositories by the end of the project, in case they continue to require access to the files stored there.

4 Datasets

In this section, the tables referring to research datasets and/or other outputs that specify their handling are provided, following the order of the WP-task numbers. Parts of the information of the data tables as they were provided to the partners were removed, because they either contained sensitive information or because they discussed points which were already addressed in the above sections of this DMP. Consequently, the data tables below contain only information that is specific to the respective datasets of the related WPs-Tasks.

The Annex of this document includes the template of the dataset tables and the instructions that were provided to the partners.

The data tables presented below were updated for the DMP V3.0 (M36). They are not yet the final data tables, but they are expected to become more detailed as the DMP gets further updated along the project lifetime. Also, further tables may be added in cases in which currently unforeseen datasets (not previously planned for) are created for the project development. Especially the issue of ethical aspects and Intellectual Property (IP) definition and management are yet in a preliminary stage for NET-Fuels.

Potential ethical or legal issues connected with data collection or data sharing, such as data compromising the safety of individuals or groups or other sensitive data have been carefully considered by the partners, and no problematic issues have so far been detected, but will continue to be monitored closely. Further, the clarification of IP ownership and protection will be explored in depth, guided by REACH in the Exploitation task T6.4 of WP6, and the data tables will be amended in accordance with its results.

4.1 Data Tables WP1

WP1 Tasks 1.1, 1.2, 1.4 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	T1.1 Scientific, financial and administrative project management T1.2 Internal communication (intranet), Communication with EAB and with the EC T1.4 Quality and risk control and ethical compliance
Dataset name	Project Management Data
Task & data manager	UNIBO
Other partners involved	All project partners
Dataset description	This dataset contains all data that is collected and generated in connection with the project's management. It is mainly of textual and numerical type. Notable output of these tasks is a project Management Plan (PMP, D1.1) which was prepared in M2 and which contains the latest version of the work plan (updated at regular intervals), the deadlines of the deliverables, the procedures to be followed for financial management and project management, partner contact details and all other information to support the management of the project. This dataset also contains data regarding all official project meetings (agendas, invitations, minutes and action lists). Further, all data connected with quality and risk mitigation control are part of this dataset.

	As the data contained in this dataset is project-specific, it is not of use to third parties.
Availability	Consortium
Data handling standards	N/A
Metadata	N/A
Data sharing	When finalized, data will be stored on the project SharePoint, only shared within the consortium. Before sharing, it will be stored on the institutional repository of UNIBO.
Persistent identifier	N/A
File formats	N/A
File scale	10 GB
Copyright & IP management	N/A
Ethical issues management	Personal data of the project members, as well as the project’s networking partners is treated in accordance with the EU GDPR legislation [19].

WP1 Task 1.3 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	Data Management
Dataset name	Data Management
Task & data manager	REACH
Other partners involved	All project partners, especially each institution’s DMO.
Dataset description	<p>Task 1.3 has the purpose of developing a project-specific data management plan (DMP, D1.2, Versions V1.0, V2.0, V3.0, V4.0), which will be regularly updated throughout the project lifetime. For this purpose, data from the partners will be collected concerning the data and other outputs of their WP tasks.</p> <p>The final deliverable (DMP) is useful to other projects, especially to those operating under the Horizon Europe framework. Further, the DMP is useful to all researchers and stakeholders interested in any of the NET-Fuels project’s results, as it enables them to easily understand the data structure and handling of the entire project.</p> <p>Due to the project-specific nature of the task, existing data cannot be reused. However, for the creation of the DMP, a template from Horizon Europe will be used.</p>

Availability	The data used to prepare the data management plan will be only available to the <u>consortium</u> . The final versions of the deliverable (DMP) will be <u>public</u> .
Data handling standards	The EC encourages DMPs to be publicly available and shared via trusted repositories. The publication of the DMP via Zenodo will be followed as best practice standard. The DMP template from Horizon Europe is used for developing the content.
Metadata	Keywords: DMP, Data Management Plan, FAIR data, Open Science, Project Management.
Data sharing	Preparatory data will be stored on REACH’s institutional repository and partly also on the project’s SharePoint. The DMP will be publicly shared via Zenodo (at a later date), as D1.2-DMP-V1.0 [20]. The first version will be available in M6, then regular updates will be released, at least three extra versions in total (DMP Version 1.0: April 2023; Version2.0: June 2024, Version 3.0: December 2025, and Version 4.0: December 2026). The three last versions of the NET-Fuels DMP will be shared immediately after completion (no embargo).
Persistent identifier	The final versions of the DMP will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	pdf, rtf, xls
File scale	Max. 100 MB
Copyright & IP management	The rights to the created DMP belong to the partners jointly. A CC-BY license will be assigned to the DMP deliverables and will be indicated in the metadata of the data via Zenodo/ARGOS. Metadata will have a CC0 licence. No IPR protection will be sought for this data set.
Ethical issues management	Personal data of the project members is treated in accordance with the EU GDPR legislation [19].

4.2 Data Tables WP2

WP2 Task 2.1 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	Feedstock supply, pre-treatment and characterization
Dataset name	Feedstock Analysis
Task & data manager	FRA

Other partners involved	ITHAKA (manages feedstock supply)
Dataset description	<p>This data set contains sample data with feedstock analysis results. A wide range of relevant feedstock is covered, from woody biomass residues over prunings to residues from agriculture and livestock farming. These are specifically anaerobic digestate, corn (maize) silage, wine pruning, hops offcuts, olive pressing residue, olive stones, pollard willow wood and burl wood. These show characterization of immediacy analysis, loss on ignition, dry residue, elemental analysis (carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, sulphur, chlorine, bromine, other elements), calorific value, ash composition (incl. declaration analyses) and determination of bulk density.</p> <p>Loss of ignition and dry residue are standardized tests performed in a muffle furnace. Elemental analysis is performed with an elemental measuring machine. The calorific value is measured in a bomb calorimeter based on DIN 51900, or according to EN 15170: 2009-05 or DIN EN ISO 18125: 2017-08. Ash composition is measured by X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy. Bulk densities are measured in a similar manner to standardized measuring methods given by the BGK method book, DIN EN ISO 17828:2016-05, or simply by settling and weighing 1000 ml samples.</p> <p>This dataset's purpose is to provide input for Task 2.4 TCR-char characterization and evaluation of potential application in the soil as amendment and carbon sink. The input is needed to be able to evaluate expected results of E.R 1 defining the exemplary biogenic residues and of E.R 3 by characterizing the feedstocks for the C-sink assessment of the NET-Fuel approach. The characterization is needed to be able to generate carbon removal certificates.</p> <p>There is similar, existing data for other feedstocks (different sample materials). Reuse of existing data has not been discarded, since it may be useful to complement the data gained from these analyses. The new data set is required to enable identification of any differences relevant to the feedstock used in this project, so it is necessary to perform specific analyses for the feedstock evaluated in this project.</p> <p>The data provides useful information to related institutes such as Biochar research Europe, UK biochar research center, Fraunhofer IBP, DBFZ and VTT.</p> <p>As further output of this task, the deliverable D2.1 (Report on feedstock characterization) is based on this dataset, summarizing the findings of the analysis performed.</p>
Availability	Public.
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Keywords: Feedstock analysis, anaerobic digestate, maize silage, corn silage, wine pruning, hops offcuts, olive pressing residue, olive stones, pollard willow wood, burl wood, immediacy analysis, loss on ignition, dry residue, elemental analysis, calorific value, ash composition, bulk density.
Data sharing	<p>After completion of Task 2.1, data will only be shared with ITHAKA on the institutional repository of FRA and on request with the consortium (to be decided) until publication of the deliverable D2.1.</p> <p>The data will be publicly shared via Zenodo together with the deliverable D2.1 (Report on feedstock characterization) after publication.</p> <p>The data will link to the project homepage, the project's research and outputs. Readme files that explain the purpose and context of the data will be provided. The data tables will have clear headers and column identifiers as is standard with data tables.</p> <p>Only a PDF viewer, internet browser for HTML and an XML editor is needed to read the data. The rest of the data is in plaintext. No tools or documentation necessary.</p>
Persistent identifier	The final versions of the data and the deliverable will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).

File formats	PDF, HTML, XML
File scale	5 MB
Copyright & IP management	The rights to the created data belong to FRA. CC-BY license will be assigned to the dataset and the deliverable and will be indicated in the metadata of the data via Zenodo. Metadata will have a CC0 license. No IPR protection will be sought for this data set.
Ethical issues management	None.

WP2 Task 2.2 Dataset 1/2	
Task title	Modelling and design of oxyfuel combustion and heat transfer to TCR
Dataset name	Oxycombustion chamber CFD simulations
Task manager	SUT
Other partners involved	FRA, LEITAT
Dataset description	<p>The aim of task 2.2 is to optimize oxy-combustion chamber and to optimize heat transfer from hot flue gases to the TCR feedstock. The first dataset (1/2) refers to the optimization of oxy-combustion process in which process combustible gases from TCR reactor will be burned in oxygen in order to generate hot flue gases which will be then used for heating TCR reactor and for supplying CO₂ to the biological processes.</p> <p>Data can be classified as generated from test models studying actual or theoretical systems. Similar data does not exist at the moment.</p> <p>Since for the optimization commercial software namely Ansys code will be used this dataset will consist of files containing numerical mesh of analysed combustion chamber as well as the files with temperatures, composition, velocities etc of gases inside the combustion chamber.</p> <p>The data will be used to prepare the deliverable D2.2 (Report on CFD model and simulations on oxyfuel combustion and heat transfer).</p>
Availability	Consortium
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Keywords: Biomass conversion modelling, heat transfer modelling, TCR, CFD Simulation
Data sharing	<p>Data will be stored on the institutional repository of SUT and will be available only for the consortium since they will contain detailed construction of the oxy-combustion burner, which is restricted know-how of WS Wärmeprozessstechnik GmbH, and cannot be shared with external entities.</p> <p>Dataset will be available in September 2024 and an entry of its existence will be created on Zenodo.</p> <p>Ansys code will be required to read and analyse data.</p>

Persistent identifier	DOI assigned by Zenodo.
File formats	Files will be in the format specific for Ansys code and will be enabled to be used for the owners of the license of the code.
File scale	File size is estimated to be about 100 GB
Copyright & IP management	According to NET-Fuels' consortium agreement, rights to the data will belong to those who were involved in their creation (FRA and SUT). No CC license is foreseen since the dataset will be for the consortium only. The metadata will have a CC0 licence.
Ethical issues management	None.

WP2 Task 2.2 Dataset 2/2	
Task title	Modelling and design of oxyfuel combustion and heat transfer to TCR
Dataset name	Heat transfer in TCR CFD simulations
Task & data manager	SUT
Other partners involved	FRA, LEITAT
Dataset description	<p>The aim of the task 2.2 is to optimize oxy-combustion chamber and to optimize heat transfer from hot flue gases to the TCR feedstock. The second dataset (2/2) refers to the optimization of heat transfer from the flue gases to TCR reactor.</p> <p>Data can be classified as generated from test models studying actual or theoretical systems. Similar data does not exist at the moment.</p> <p>As for the optimization commercial software, namely Ansys code, will be used, this dataset will consist of files containing numerical mesh of analysed heat transfer zones as well as the files with temperatures, velocities etc, of heating gases and feedstock.</p> <p>The data will be used to prepare the deliverable D2.2 (Report on CFD model and simulations on oxyfuel combustion and heat transfer).</p>
Availability	Consortium
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Keywords: Biomass conversion modelling, heat transfer modelling TCR, CFD Simulation
Data sharing	<p>Data will be stored on the institutional repository of SUT and will be available only for the consortium since they will contain detailed construction of the TCR reactor, which is protected know-how of FRA and cannot be shared with external entities. The deliverable D2.2 will therefore not be made public.</p> <p>Data will be available in September 2024 and an entry of its existence will be created on Zenodo.</p> <p>Ansys code will be required to read and analyse data.</p>

Persistent identifier	The final versions of data will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	Files will be in the format specific for Ansys code and will be enabled to be used for owners of the license of the code.
File scale	Estimated to 5 TB
Copyright & IP management	According to NET-Fuels’ consortium agreement, rights to the data will belong to those who were involved in their creation (FRA and SUT). No CC license is foreseen since data will be available for the consortium only. The metadata of this dataset will have a CCO licence.
Ethical issues management	None.

WP2 Task 2.3 Dataset 1/2	
Task title	Thermo-chemical conversion and oxyfuel combustion tests
Dataset name	Carbon Dioxide Analysis
Task & data manager	FRA
Other partners involved	SUT, LEITAT, ITHAKA, REACH
Dataset description	<p>This dataset contains analysis data of the produced CO₂ from the oxyfuel combustion process and after CO₂ purification. The CO₂ is produced by the oxyfuel combustion of pyrolysis plant gas. The pyrolysis feedstock is composed of digestate from anaerobic digestion of manure and corn silage, calamity wood and prunings. First data sets from plant operation and deliverable D2.3 (Report on plant operation performance with mass and energy balance) are also provided.</p> <p>The data is gained by performing a gas analysis of CO₂ stream from oxy-fuel combustion with online analysis sensors and gas chromatography.</p> <p>The overall purpose of WP2 to which this task contributes, is to provide a technical assessment of a combined approach for the production of biofuel, H₂ and biochar in combination with CO₂ capture from oxy-combustion in terms of product quality, process stability and efficiency.</p> <p>The purpose of this dataset is to provide input for WP3 (Bioelectrochemical process for CO₂ conversion to CH₄ from off-gas streams). The input is needed to ensure tolerance of the reactor of the bioelectrochemical process to the input stream. Also, regarding CO₂ capture from the oxy-combustion exhaust gas, the objective is to achieve a high quality of CO₂ separation with a total impurity of (O₂, SO₂, NO_x, CO) lower than 4-5%, optimized for later utilization in the BEM unit. The new dataset is required to enable design of both the pilot BEM reactor and for preliminary up-scaling to industrial scale.</p>

	There is no similar, existing data which shows the CO ₂ quality of combustion gases from similar processes with similar feedstocks.
Availability	Public.
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Keywords: Anaerobic digestate, corn silage, calamity wood, prunings, pyrolysis, oxy-combustion, oxyfuel, CO ₂ , O ₂ , SO ₂ , NO _x , CO, flue gas, CCU - carbon capture and usage, CCUS, bioenergy with carbon capture and storage, BECCS.
Data sharing	<p>For the duration of the task (M6-M40), data will only be shared on the institutional repository of FRA with SUT, LEITAT, and ITHAKA.</p> <p>The data will be publicly shared via Zenodo at the time of the publication of the final deliverable D2.3 (report on plant operation performance with mass and energy balance) in M40.</p> <p>The data will link to the project homepage, the project's research and outputs. Readme files that explain the purpose and context of the data will be provided. The data tables will have clear headers and column identifiers as is standard with data tables.</p> <p>A PDF viewer, internet browser for HTML and an XML editor will be required to check the data. The rest of the data is in plaintext. No tools or documentation necessary.</p>
Persistent identifier	The final versions of the data will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	.rtf, .txt, .PDF, .csv, .md, .Rmd, .ipynb, HTML, XML, .zip
File scale	From 1 MB to 1 GB
Copyright & IP management	<p>The rights to the created data belong to FRA.</p> <p>CC-BY license will be assigned to the dataset and the deliverable and will be indicated in the metadata of both via Zenodo. Metadata will have a CC0 license.</p> <p>No IPR protection will be sought for this data set.</p>

WP2 Task 2.3 Dataset 2/2

Task title	Thermo-chemical conversion and oxyfuel combustion tests
Dataset name	Mass Energy Balance
Task & data manager	FRA

Other partners involved	SUT, LEITAT, ITHAKA, REACH
Dataset description	<p>Energy and mass balance assessing the performance of the TCR pilot plant with pyrolysis, hydrogen separation and oxyfuel combustion. The pyrolysis feedstock is composed of digestate from anaerobic digestion of manure and corn silage, calamity wood and prunings.</p> <p>The data is gained by means of measurements of temperature, pressure, volumetric flow rates, masses, compositions of feedstock and of process streams by means of line analysis and of gas chromatograph results. These will be converted into mass and energy flows via interpolation, estimation and balancing.</p> <p>Quality is assured by the consideration of multiple, dissimilar measurement sources in balancing of mass and energy with a statistically most probable result. The naturally resulting dissimilar redundancy ensures representative results.</p> <p>The purpose of the task is to assess the performances of the system. Additional purposes are to provide input to the LCIA analysis for work package WP4 and to the work package WP5 (Business Development and Potential Industrial Scale-up) by allowing estimates of mass and energy flows at an industrial scale.</p> <p>The input is needed to be able to evaluate expected results of E.R 2: Numerical models and blueprints to make the single process units interoperable in a variety of conditions. The mass and energy balances are needed to be able to generate carbon removal certificates.</p> <p>This dataset contributes to the general objective of WP2 of providing a technical assessment of a combined approach for the production of biofuel, H₂ and biochar in combination with CO₂ capture from oxy-combustion in terms of product quality, process stability and efficiency. The new data set is required for preliminary up-scaling to industrial scale and to provide input to the LCIA analysis.</p> <p>There is no similar, existing data which shows the mass and energy balances from similar processes with similar feedstocks.</p> <p>The data provides useful information to related institutes, such as Biochar research Europe, UK biochar research center, Fraunhofer IBP, DBFZ and VTT.</p>
Availability	Public.
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Keywords: Anaerobic digestate, corn silage, calamity wood, prunings, pyrolysis, oxy-combustion, oxyfuel, carbon capture and usage, CCU, bioenergy with carbon capture and storage, BECCS, mass balancing, energy balancing, process modelling, process simulation, Sankey diagrams, mass flows, energy flows.

Data sharing	<p>For the duration of the task (M6-M40), data will only be shared on the institutional repository of FRA with SUT, LEITAT, and ITHAKA.</p> <p>The data will be publicly shared via Zenodo at the time of the publication of the final deliverable D2.3 (report on plant operation performance with mass and energy balance) in M40.</p> <p>The data will link to the project homepage, the project’s research and outputs. Readme files that explain the purpose and context of the data will be provided. The data tables will have clear headers and column identifiers as is standard with data tables.</p> <p>Only a PDF viewer, internet browser for HTML and an XML editor. The rest of the data is in plaintext. No tools or documentation necessary.</p>
Persistent identifier	The final versions of the data and deliverable will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	.rtf, .txt, .PDF, .csv, .md, .Rmd, .ipynb, HTML, XML, .zip
File scale	From 1 MB to 1 GB
Copyright & IP management	<p>The rights to the created data belong to FRA.</p> <p>CC-BY license will be assigned to the dataset and the deliverable and will be indicated in the metadata of the data via Zenodo. Metadata will have a CC0 license.</p> <p>No IPR protection will be sought for this dataset.</p>

WP2 Task 2.4 Dataset 1/2	
Task title	TCR-char characterization and evaluation of potential application in the soil as amendment and carbon sink
Dataset name	TCR char properties
Task & data manager	ITHAKA
Other partners involved	FRA
Dataset description	<p>TCR-char will be characterized according to the guidelines of the European Biochar Certificate, which will be complemented by additional analysis. Data will include chemical composition (e.g., % carbon content, % ash content, etc.) and related properties like pH and conductivity.</p> <p>The data is used to show the test the compliance with EU Fertilizer Product Regulation (EU 2019/1009) and the EBC biochar certification scheme. Data on elemental composition is necessary for the calculation of the carbon sink in WP 4 (LCA/certification). Moreover, it is used to compare TCR-char with other, EBC certified biochar available on the market to demonstrate that TCR-char can be accepted on the market.</p> <p>The data is of interest to potential users/investors of the TCR-process and to the biochar science community. Up to date, limit information is published on TCR-char and no data is available on TCR-char from the specific feedstocks.</p>

Availability	Public.
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Keywords: biochar, PyCCS, pyrogenic carbon capture and storage, biochar carbon removal, BCR, pyrolysis
Data sharing	For the duration of the task, data will only be shared on the institutional repository of ITHAKA within the consortium. The data will be publicly shared via Zenodo at the time of the publication of the final deliverable D2.4 (report on plant operation performance with mass and energy balance) in M45. The deliverable will also be published in Zenodo. The data and deliverable will link to the project homepage, the project’s research and outputs. Readme files that explain the purpose and context of the data will be provided. The data tables will have clear headers and column identifiers. Only a PDF and spreadsheet viewer is necessary to read data. No tools are necessary.
Persistent identifier	The final versions of the data and deliverable will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	*.pdf, *. *.csv
File scale	10-100 MB
Copyright & IP management	The rights to the created data belong to ITHAKA. CC-BY license will be assigned to the dataset and the deliverable and will be indicated in the metadata of the data via Zenodo. Metadata will have a CC0 license. No IPR protection will be sought for this dataset.

WP2 Task 2.4 Dataset 2/2	
Task title	TCR-char characterization and evaluation of potential application in the soil as amendment and carbon sink
Dataset name	Agronomic data of TCR-char
Task & data manager	ITHAKA
Other partners involved	None.
Dataset description	TCR-char will be used in agronomic pot and field trials to test its agronomic performance. TCR-chars might be pretreated (milled, suspended, and/or combined with nutrients). Experiments will be multi-factorial: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) type of biochar (no – TCR-char from different feedstock, commercial biochar). (2) Pretreatment of biochar, combination with nutrients. (3) Crop / plants grown in the trial. <p>Not all experiments will cover all factors. Data will include plant height and data on leaf color/pigments (SPAD) over time, above and below ground biomass at harvest, root architecture.</p>

	The data is of interest to potential users/investors of the TCR-process, potential buyers of the TCR-char and to the biochar science community. Up to date, there is no published data on agronomic performance of TCR-chars.
Availability	Public.
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Keywords: biochar, biochar-based fertiliz*, pyrogenic fertiliz*, PyCCS, pyrogenic carbon capture and storage, biochar carbon removal, BCR.
Data sharing	The data will be publicly shared via Zenodo at the time of the publication of the final deliverable D2.4 (report on plant operation performance with mass and energy balance) in M45. The data will link to the project homepage, the project’s research and outputs. Readme files that explain the purpose and context of the data will be provided. The data tables will have clear headers and column identifiers. Only a PDF, TIFF, and spreadsheet viewer is necessary. No tools necessary.
Persistent identifier	The final versions of the data and deliverable will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	*.pdf, *.jpg, *.tiff, *.csv
File scale	1 GB
Copyright & IP management	The rights to the created data belong to ITHAKA. CC-BY license will be assigned to the dataset and the deliverable and will be indicated in the metadata of the data via Zenodo. Metadata will have a CC0 license. No IPR protection will be sought for this dataset.

4.3 Data Tables WP3

WP3 Task 3.1 Dataset 1/2	
Task title	Reactor design, construction and start-up
Dataset name	Reactor Design
Task & data manager	LEITAT
Other partners involved	No other participant.
Dataset description	This dataset contains as output the design of a BEM reactor and methane separation unit (settler) aimed at fostering high-purity biogas production (95% CH ₄ content). Furthermore, it includes a list of specifications for the different components of the reactor. This dataset will be used to contribute to D3.1. Data from literature review will be gathered and reused.

Availability	Consortium.
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Keywords: BEM Reactor; Reactor Design; Reactor Construction; Methane separation; Biogas
Data sharing	The design data will be stored in the institutional repository of LEITAT for internal use and made available to consortium members as needed. The data will not be shared outside the consortium for IP protection reasons
Persistent identifier	N/A
File formats	*.SLDPRT;*.dxf; *.pdf; *.xlsx; *.docx; *.pptx
File scale	Less than 1GB
Copyright & IP management	LEITAT collects and generates the data and is therefore the owner of this dataset. The generated data of this dataset will be produced by LEITAT, using part of its background knowledge and will therefore also be owned by LEITAT.

WP3 Task 3.1 Dataset 2/2	
Task title	Reactor design, construction and start-up
Dataset name	Reactor start-up
Task & data manager	LEITAT
Other partners involved	No other participant
Dataset description	This dataset contains data from the start-up of the BEM reactors. The process will be monitored for CO ₂ conversion, current density, biomethane purity, and production rate. A detailed protocol for the start-up experiments and a file summarizing all the results will be produced. This dataset will be used to contribute to D3.1 (Report on construction, performance and optimization of BEM reactors).
Availability	Consortium.
Data handling standards	None.

Metadata	Keywords: bioelectrochemical reactor design, electromethanogenesis, cell components, inoculation, start-up protocol, biomethane, biocathode
Data sharing	Data generated by LEITAT researchers will be stored in the institutional repository of LEITAT for internal use and made available to consortium members as needed. In M14 an entry of the dataset’s existence will be created on Zenodo.
Persistent identifier	The dataset 2/2 of this task will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	*.SLDPRT;*.dxf; *.pdf; *.xlsx; *.docx; *.pptx
File scale	Less than 1GB
Copyright & IP management	LEITAT collects the data and is therefore the owner of this dataset. The generated data of this dataset will be produced by LEITAT, using part of its background knowledge and will therefore also be owned by LEITAT. The metadata of the dataset will carry a CC0 licence.

WP3 Task 3.2 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	BEM process optimization
Dataset name	BEM process optimization
Task & data manager	LEITAT
Other partners involved	UNIBO, REACH
Dataset description	<p>This dataset contains the data resulting from the optimization of BEM reactor process. Different separator-anolyte pairs will be tested to identify the optimal components of the pilot plant, aiming at minimizing the internal resistance of the BEM reactor. Furthermore, mass and electron balance from the laboratory scale BEM operation will be included. Different electrical control strategies will be tested to optimize the kinetic behaviour of the BEM reactor in a scenario of powering it with renewable energy surpluses.</p> <p>The dataset will also include data regarding the optimization of the CO₂ dissolution in the system using membrane contactors. The aim is to maximize the CO₂ feeding and concentration in the liquid phase, while minimizing the CO₂ desorption to the gas phase, which would contaminate the produced methane, lowering the purity grade. Data gathered during this development phase will be employed by REACH for modelling activity in WP5.</p> <p>This dataset will contain also data on planktonic and biofilm-related communities from 16S rRNA gene sequence analysis. These will be used to improve the microbe-cathode interaction in BEM reactor.</p> <p>This dataset will be used to contribute to D3.2 (Report on design, construction and operation of BEM pilot plant). Data from literature review will also be gathered and reused.</p>

Availability	Consortium.
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Keywords: process optimization, electromethanogenesis, CO ₂ conversion, pilot plant, e-fuels, synthetic-methane
Data sharing	Data generated by LEITAT researchers will be stored in the institutional repository of LEITAT for internal use and made available to consortium members as needed. Data and the deliverable D3.2 will not be shared outside the consortium, due to protection of relevant IP. In M24 an entry of the dataset's existence will be created on Zenodo.
Persistent identifier	The dataset of this task will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	*.pdf; *.xlsx; *.docx; *.pptx
File scale	Less than 1GB
Copyright & IP management	LEITAT collects the data generated in laboratory experiments and is therefore the owner of this dataset. The generated data of this dataset will be produced by LEITAT, using part of its background knowledge and will therefore also be owned by LEITAT. The metadata of the dataset will carry a CC0 licence.

WP3 Task 3.3 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	Technology piloting with real gas effluents
Dataset name	Technology Piloting
Task & data manager	LEITAT
Other partners involved	FRA
Dataset description	This dataset contains the data gained from BEM technology piloting with real gas effluents. Electrochemical and physic-chemical parameters will be tested. The use of real effluents and the analysis of the changes in the CO ₂ conversion performance, due to impurities (e.g. CO and O ₂) present in the gas feed, are essential for this project. This dataset will be used to contribute to D3.2. Besides, data from literature review will be gathered and reused.
Availability	Consortium.

Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Keywords: technology piloting, process optimization, electromethanogenesis, CO ₂ conversion, industrial gaseous effluents, gas impurities, process resistance, process resilience, industrial integration
Data sharing	Data generated by LEITAT researchers will be stored in the institutional repository of LEITAT for internal use and made available to consortium members as needed. In M36 an entry of the dataset's existence will be created on Zenodo.
Persistent identifier	The dataset of this task will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	*.pdf; *.xlsx; *.docx; *.pptx
File scale	Less than 1GB
Copyright & IP management	LEITAT and FRAUNHOFER will collect the data generated in laboratory experiments and are, therefore, the owner of their respective datasets.

WP3 Task 3.4 Dataset 1/2	
Task title	BEM operation and validation
Dataset name	Methane Analysis
Task & data manager	FRA
Other partners involved	LEITAT
Dataset description	<p>This data set contains the data from the Bioelectrochemical process for CO₂ conversion to CH₄ from off-gas streams. The CH₄ is produced from CO₂ made by oxyfuel combustion of pyrolysis plant gas. The pyrolysis feedstock comprises digestate from anaerobic digestion of manure and corn silage, calamity wood, and pruning. It provides information about the CH₄ gas quality.</p> <p>The data is acquired information about the efficiency, energy storage and CO₂ conversion capacity, CH₄ production rate and gas quality from the Bioelectrochemical process.</p> <p>The purpose of this data is to generate enough data quality and quantity to undertake the modelling task (task T4.2). The input is needed to calibrate the simulations in the modelling task.</p> <p>The objective is to validate at TRL 5 an integrated pilot scale system with a capacity of 30 kg/hour of waste biogenic feedstock, monitored with real-time analysis tools for optimal performance and providing an innovative solution for biofuel production from residue streams.</p>

	<p>WP3 General Objective: Design, build, operate and optimize the BEM reactor for the bio-electrochemical conversion of CO₂ into CH₄, valorising the emissions of the TCR process (WP2), with the ambition of accomplishing a zero-emission process.</p> <p>The new data set is required to enable design of both the pilot BEM reactor and for preliminary up-scaling to industrial scale. There is no similar, existing data which shows the CH₄ quality of combustion gases from similar processes with similar feedstocks.</p> <p>LEITAT will participate in setting up and operating the integrated pilot plant. LEITAT is responsible and owns the bioelectrochemical process.</p>
Availability	Consortium.
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Keywords: Anaerobic digestate, corn silage, calamity wood, prunings, pyrolysis, oxy-combustion, oxyfuel, CO ₂ , CH ₄ , BEM, Bioelectrochemical methanation, carbon capture and usage, CCU, bioenergy with carbon capture and storage, BECCS.
Data sharing	<p>For the duration of Task 3.4 (M30-M46) data will only be shared on the institutional repository of FRA with LEITAT and shared also with the consortium on request. This dataset will be used to contribute to D3.2.</p> <p>The data used in the associated public deliverable will be uploaded to Zenodo. In M46 an entry of the dataset's existence will be created on Zenodo.</p>
Persistent identifier	The dataset of this task will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	.rtf, .txt, .PDF, .csv, .md, .Rmd, .ipynb, HTML, XML, .zip
File scale	From 1 MB to 1 GB
Copyright & IP management	<p>The rights to the created data belong to FRA and LEITAT.</p> <p>Metadata will have a CC0 license.</p> <p>IPR protection will be sought for the results of this WP.</p>

WP3 Task 3.4 Dataset 2/2	
Task title	BEM operation and validation
Dataset name	Mass Energy Balance
Task & data manager	FRA
Other partners involved	LEITAT
Dataset description	This dataset contains data on the efficiency, energy storage and CO ₂ conversion capacity, CH ₄ production rate from the Bioelectrochemical process for CO ₂ conversion to CH ₄ from

	<p>off-gas streams. The CH₄ is produced from CO₂ made by oxyfuel combustion of pyrolysis plant gas. The pyrolysis feedstock is composed of digestate from anaerobic digestion of manure and corn silage, calamity wood and prunings. It provides information about the CH₄ bioelectrochemical process mass balance.</p> <p>The data is gained through measurements of temperature, pressure, volumetric flow rates, masses, compositions of feedstock and of process streams for the bioelectrochemical process. These will be converted into mass and energy flows via interpolation, estimation and balancing.</p> <p>Quality is assured by the consideration of multiple, dissimilar measurement sources in balancing of mass and energy with a statistically most probable result. The naturally resulting dissimilar redundancy ensures representative results.</p> <p>Its purpose is to be used as input to calibrate the simulations in the modelling task.</p> <p>The general objective of the task is to validate at TRL 5 an integrated pilot scale system with a capacity of 30 kg/hour of waste biogenic feedstock, providing an innovative solution for biofuel production from residue streams.</p> <p>WP3 General Objective: Design, build, operate and optimize the BEM reactor for the bio-electrochemical conversion of CO₂ into CH₄, valorising the emissions of the TCR process (WP2), with the ambition of accomplishing a zero-emission process.</p> <p>The new data set is required to enable design of both the pilot BEM reactor and for preliminary up-scaling to industrial scale. There is no similar, existing data which shows the mass balance of CH₄ quality from combustion gases from similar processes with similar feedstocks.</p> <p>LEITAT will participate in setting up and operating the integrated pilot plant, and is responsible and owns the bioelectrochemical process.</p> <p>This dataset will be used to contribute to D3.2.</p>
Availability	Consortium.
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Keywords: Anaerobic digestate, corn silage, calamity wood, prunings, pyrolysis, oxy-combustion, oxyfuel, CO ₂ , CH ₄ , BEM, Bioelectrochemical methanation, carbon capture and usage, CCU, bioenergy with carbon capture and storage, BECCS, mass balancing, energy balancing, process modelling, process simulation, Sankey diagrams, mass flows, energy flows.
Data sharing	<p>For the duration of the task (M30-M46), data will only be shared on the institutional repository of FRA with LEITAT and shared with the consortium on request.</p> <p>The data used in the associated public deliverable will be uploaded to Zenodo. In M46 an entry of the dataset's existence will be created on Zenodo.</p> <p>The data will link to the project homepage, the project's research and outputs. The data tables will have clear headers and column identifiers as is standard with data tables.</p> <p>Only a PDF viewer, internet browser for HTML and an XML editor. The rest of the data is in plain text. No tools or documentation necessary. Data with models from specialized programs, either proprietary or open source, may be added.</p>
Persistent identifier	The dataset of this task will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).

File formats	.rtf, .txt, .PDF, .csv, .md, .Rmd, .ipynb, HTML, XML, .zip
File scale	From 1 MB to 1 GB
Copyright & IP management	The rights to the created data belong to FRA and LEITAT. Metadata will have a CC0 licence. IPR protection will be sought for the results of this WP.

4.4 Data Tables WP4

WP4 Task 4.1 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	Ensure reproducibility, transparency, and comparability of the sustainability assessment
Dataset name	Sustainability Assessment
Task & data manager	UNIBO
Other partners involved	SUT, ITHAKA, WRG, REACH, FRA, LEITAT
Dataset description	<p>Task 4.1 aims at providing a common ground (methods, uniformity of intentions, audience) and framework for sustainability assessments, in order to contribute to the objective of proving negative GHG emissions and higher sustainability potential of biofuel production when reusing biogenic effluent gases in-situ, along with addressing socioeconomic aspects.</p> <p>Its output will be a framework for sustainability assessment, which will be reported in deliverable D4.1 (Methodologies for the sustainability analysis of the NET-Fuels technology).</p> <p>The deliverable will cover (a) system boundaries from the collection of the feedstock; (b) reference biofuel production systems for the comparison with NET-Fuels performances; (c) time horizon of the analysis with reference to the time scale for carbon sink; (d) preliminary definition of the functional units (e.g. process or product oriented); (e) preliminary identification and selection of scenarios and product-system variations with regard to feedstocks and number of impact categories; (f) preliminary decision about impact categories and characterization models in preparation for Task 4.2; (g) data flow, data sources and data sharing between the tasks in WP4.</p>
Availability	Public
Data handling standards	None.

Metadata	Keywords: sustainability assessment, framework, negative GHG emissions, reproducibility, transparency, comparability, LCI, LCIA, LCA, inventory, system boundaries, production system, functional units, scenarios, impact categories
Data sharing	Supporting data necessary to prepare the deliverable was stored on the institutional repository of UNIBO and will be shared with the partners via the project's SharePoint. The deliverable was made public via Zenodo in M12.
Persistent identifier	The final version of the deliverable received a PID from Zenodo (DOI): https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10058004
File formats	Deliverable will be stored as open access formats: .csv, .rtf, .txt or .pdf
File scale	From 1 MB to 10 MB
Copyright & IP management	The deliverable will receive a CC-BY license; its metadata will receive a CC0 licence.

WP4 Task 4.2 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	Ensure comprehensiveness and relevance to the project
Dataset name	Life Cycle Inventory & Impact Indicators
Task & data manager	SUT
Other partners involved	ITHAKA, UNIBO, FRA, LEITAT
Dataset description	<p>The dataset is two-part: the first part includes the Life Cycle Inventory numerical data. The second part includes a list of chosen impact categories together with assignment of inventory results to environmental impact categories and indicators.</p> <p>The data generated in this task will form part of D4.2 NET-Fuels LCIA interpretation.</p> <p>The dataset is needed for dynamic LCIA in T4.3. The LCIA results are indispensable for reliable assessment of the proposed technology and potential benchmarking.</p> <p>Although based partially on secondary data, this dataset is unique because of the technological novelty of the analyzed system itself.</p>
Availability	Public
Data handling standards	Data collection for the Life Cycle Inventory, their analysis and representation by Impact Indicators is normalized by the ISO-14040 standards.
Metadata	Keywords: LCI, LCIA, LCA, inventory, impact indicators, impact categories, environmental assessment

Data sharing	This data set will be stored on the institutional repository of SUT and inventory data will be shared with UNIBO for T4.3 purposes, and will be used for scientific publications which will also be shared by Zenodo. D4.2 will be made public via Zenodo in M46.
Persistent identifier	The final version of the deliverable will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	Data will be stored in Excel files, will be exported to xml or csv format for the public versions.
File scale	Up to 2 GB
Copyright & IP management	According to the consortium agreement, rights to the data will belong to those who were involved in their creation. CC-BY license is assigned for the dataset (based on secondary data originating from CC-BY sources) CC0 license is assigned for the metadata.

WP4 Task 4.3 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	Ensure validity over time and under different conditions
Dataset name	Dynamic environmental impact assessment
Task & data manager	UNIBO
Other partners involved	SUT, ITHAKA (collaboration in the task activities)
Dataset description	Task 4.3 aims at studying in detail the effects of the NET-Fuels technology (especially GHG emissions) considering relevant conditions (parameters) of the feedstock, operations and case studies in time and localisation, considering the future changes in the production of energy and the sustainability policies implemented in the E.U. Its output will consist of a parametric model building upon the LCI model (T4.2) to compute the GHGs emissions. The deliverable D4.3 (NET-Fuels dynamic environmental impact assessment and GHG emission calculation), with an explanation on how the parametric model was assembled, and the sensitivity analysis performed with it, to identify and select 4 to 10 key parameters affecting the GHGs balance.
Availability	Public
Data handling standards	Data collection for the Impact Assessment, including Life Cycle Inventory data analysis and representation by Impact Indicators, is normalized by the ISO-14040 standards.

Metadata	Keywords: parametric model, future energy production, sensitivity analysis, GHG emissions, LCI.
Data sharing	Supporting data necessary to prepare the deliverable will be stored on the institutional repository of UNIBO and will be shared with the partners via the project's SharePoint. The deliverable D4.3 will be made public via Zenodo in M46.
Persistent identifier	The final version of the deliverable D4.3 will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	Deliverable D4.3 will be stored as open access formats: .csv, .rtf, .txt or .pdf
File scale	From 1 MB to 1 GB
Copyright & IP management	The deliverable will receive a CC-BY license; its metadata a CC0 licence.

WP4 Task 4.4 Dataset 1/1

Task title	Studying NET-Fuels impact in the society
Dataset name	Society Impact Assessment
Task & data manager	UNIBO
Other partners involved	SUT, ITHAKA, REACH, WRG, FRA (providing data and collaborating in the task activities)
Dataset description	<p>Task 4.4 comprises: (a) connecting NET-Fuels product system to all supply products and to corresponding sectors and uses; (b) aggregating regional data and sectors; (c) defining the limits of the industrial expansion: potential availability of residual biomass; (d) computing economic effects and interpretation; (e) computing labour effects, emission effects and resource effects. Its output consists of a simplified excel calculator to analyse the societal impacts of the Net-Fuels technology in its expansion to the maximum and minimum extension of the value generated in the economy as represented in the EXIOBASE3 database.</p> <p>The deliverable D4.4 (Socio-economic effects of the adoption of NET-Fuels), with an explanation on how the excel calculator was elaborated (The connections of NET-Fuels products to all supply products and to corresponding sectors and uses are presented using a specific database, EXIOBASE3, with 163 industry, 200 products classification, 3 employment skill levels per gender, 417 emission categories, 662 material and resources categories), and how to use it.</p>

Availability	Public
Data handling standards	Relevant sectors aggregated into specific sector categories following the United Nations International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities (ISIC) system.
Metadata	Keywords: LCI, EXIOBASE3, industrial expansion, economic effects, labour effects, emission effects, resource effects.
Data sharing	Supporting data necessary to prepare the deliverable will be stored on the institutional repository of UNIBO and will be shared with the partners via the project's SharePoint. The deliverable D4.4 will be made public via Zenodo in M40.
Persistent identifier	The final version of the deliverable D4.4 will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	Deliverable D4.4 will be stored as open access formats: .csv, .rtf, .txt or .pdf
File scale	From 1 MB to 1 GB
Copyright & IP management	The deliverable will receive a CC-BY license; its metadata a CC0 licence.

WP4 Task 4.5 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	Qualitative study of cultural and political dimensions
Dataset name	Cultural, political, and ecological-economic implications of NET Fuels
Task & data manager	UNIBO
Other partners involved	FRA, LEITAT, ITHAKA, SUT, REACH, WRG (data providers)
Dataset description	Task 4.5 examines the cultural, political, and ecological-economic implications of NET Fuels, and will produce texts and multimedia outputs designed to stimulate a wider conversation across academic disciplines and in the public sphere. The output will consist of the deliverable D4.5 (Guideline for the Carbon sink assessment for NET-Fuels production).
Availability	Public

Data handling standards	Relevant sectors aggregated into specific sector categories following the United Nations International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities (ISIC) system.
Metadata	Keywords: transversal design principles, cultural and political dimensions, ethnographic study, anthropology, science and technology studies, ecological-economics and actor-network theory.
Data sharing	Supporting data necessary to prepare the deliverable will be stored on the institutional repository of UNIBO and will be shared with the partners via the project's SharePoint. The deliverable D4.5 will be made public via Zenodo in M46.
Persistent identifier	The final version of the deliverable D4.5 will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	Deliverable D4.5 will be stored as open access formats: .csv, .rtf, .txt or .pdf
File scale	From 1 MB to 1 GB
Copyright & IP management	The deliverable will receive a CC-BY license; its metadata a CC0 licence.

WP4 Task 4.6 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	Carbon sink assessment
Dataset name	Guidelines for carbon sink assessment
Task & data manager	ITHAKA
Other partners involved	UNIBO
Dataset description	Written guidelines on the assessment of carbon sinks created by non-oxidative use of biochar from complex production processes such as the TCR-process that co-produce multiple products including fuels . It consists of detailed description (continuous text) with exemplary calculations and may include graphs and tables.
Availability	Public
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Keywords: biochar, CDR, carbon dioxide removal, negative emission technology, PyCCS, pyrogenic carbon capture and storage, biochar carbon removal, BCR.
Data sharing	The data will be publicly shared on Zenodo at the time of the publication of the final deliverable D4.6 (report on plant operation performance with mass and energy balance) in M46.

	The data will link to the project homepage, the project’s research and outputs. Only a PDF viewer is necessary. No tools or documentation necessary.
Persistent identifier	The final version of the deliverable will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	*.pdf
File scale	1 MB
Copyright & IP management	The rights to the created data belong to ITHAKA and will probably be published under CC-BY license.

4.5 Data Tables WP5

WP5 Task 5.1 Dataset 1/2	
Task title	Market & Competitive Research
Dataset name	Market & Competitive Research and Analysis
Task & data manager	REACH
Other partners involved	UNIBO, FRA, LEITAT, ITHAKA, SUT, WRG
Dataset description	<p>General Description: This Dataset contains collected and generated data that is necessary for the production of deliverable D5.1 (NET-Fuels Market and Competitive Research Analysis) of this task. The collected data will consist of the information obtained from existing published high-quality peer-reviewed literature and/or from material stored in open access or proprietary websites. The generated data will consist of the analysis of the collected data conducted by means of respective analysis methodologies.</p> <p>Scope of the collected dataset: The research and analysis on competitive technologies will focus on the value proposition identified for NET-Fuels, namely: (a) Negative Biofuel initiatives; (b) CCUS - Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage; (c) Soil Carbon Sequestration; (d) Energy Storage; (e) Competitive Technologies’ efficiency, costs, versatility, risks and barriers; etc.</p> <p>Main objectives: This dataset will support the implementation of T5.1 by (a) obtaining project-relevant information (defined in “Scope of the collected dataset”); (b) making informed decisions for the elaboration of the Market & Research Analysis, for the development of the NET-Fuels project’s business definition and its sustainable scale-up approach at industrial level and the project exploitation. The data will be used to produce the Research & Technology Analysis, which will be considered, together with pre-defined NET-Fuels key exploitable results (KERs), for producing the project’s outcome on market evaluation.</p>

	<p>Main Types of Data: (1) Collected data: Research & Innovation Project Data; Survey Data; Experimental Data; Use-Cases Data; Research Results Data; Marketable Results Data; IPR Data; Trademark Data. (2) Generated data: Analysis of the data, esp. SWOT and PESTEL Analysis.</p> <p>Data Reuse: Existing data (mainly results from published literature) will be used within the “Technology Watch” of the task on the state of the art, including research and innovation projects and emerging new scientific breakthroughs or industrial developments in the field. A selection of the collected data will be part of deliverable D5.1 (Market & Competitive Research Analysis).</p>
Availability	Consortium
Data handling standards	The employ of the standard “ISO 20252:2019: Market, opinion and social research” is currently being considered.
Metadata	Keywords: NET; Biofuel; Bioenergy; CCUS; CCS; Energy-Storage; BEM; TCR; P2G; PyCCS; SOTA; Experimental Study; Methodology; Cost Analysis; Cost Efficiency; Risks Impact; Market Analysis, SWOT, Technology Watch, Competitive Research, Market Research.
Data sharing	<p>This dataset will be stored in a structured way (organized documents or databases), allowing navigation through initiatives, scientific breakthroughs and their names, locations, KPI, patents criteria and the results of the data analysis in the defined project SharePoint repository starting from February 2023 onwards and will be regularly updated.</p> <p>This dataset will be used to prepare the deliverable D5.1 which is classified as Sensitive (SEN) in its Dissemination level according to the Grant Agreement due to protection of IP and will therefore only be available to the Consortium. For this reason, also this preparatory dataset will only be shared within the consortium.</p> <p>The dataset will be accompanied with explanatory documents to make the collection and generation of the data transparent to the partners e.g. by citation of the original sources (including identifiers where available) or by indication of the methodology used for the data analysis.</p> <p>Before this dataset will be stored and shared among the Consortium partners in the project SharePoint, it will be stored by REACH on its institutional repository. An entry of the dataset’s existence will be created on Zenodo in M24.</p>
Persistent identifier	PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	<p>The datatypes will vary among textual (text files including images); numerical; software; and multimedia, in various formats: images, videos, etc.</p> <p>Data / File Formats: (a) Images will be stored in JPEG, PNG, TIFF or RAW formats; (b) Videos will be stored in mp4 or in .avi format; (c) spreadsheets (.xls or .csv); (d) Textual files will be either stored in PDF or in open-access converted .doc formats.</p>
File scale	10 GB (max).

Copyright & IP management	<p>REACH collects the data and is therefore the owner of this dataset. The generated data of this dataset will be produced by REACH, using part of its background knowledge and will therefore also be owned by REACH. In case of significant input by other partners, they will be the owners of the respective contributions. If the contributions from several partners cannot be separated, the partners will co-own those parts.</p> <p>No CC licenses will be applied as this dataset will not be publicly published.</p>
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WP5 Task 5.1 Dataset 2/2	
Task title	Market & Competitive Research
Dataset name	Market and Competitive Research Analysis
Task & data manager	REACH
Other partners involved	UNIBO, FRA, LEITAT, ITHAKA, SUT, WRG
Dataset description	<p>General description: This dataset consists of the deliverable “D5.1 - NET-Fuels Market and Competitive Research Analysis”, which is the main output of task T5.1.</p> <p>Scope of the dataset: The content of this output is a market intelligence research analysis on the relevant competitive technologies (e.g.: other negative biofuel initiatives, CCUS, soil carbon sequestration, energy storage), their KPIs, as well as their corresponding SWOT analysis and their relation to NET-Fuels.</p> <p>Main objectives & usage: The main objective of D5.1 is to summarize and synthesize the findings of T5.1 and to function as valuable input source for T5.2 (Business model development & Business plan), T5.4 (System scale-up for industrial scale) and T6.4 (exploitation of the project).</p> <p>Main type of generated data: The main data type will be textual including illustrations.</p> <p>Data reuse: Data will be used for the production of deliverable D5.1, mainly results from published literature and from datasets WP5-T5.1-1/2.</p>
Availability	<p>Consortium</p> <p>Deliverable D5.1 is classified as Sensitive (SEN) in its Dissemination level according to the Grant Agreement due to protection of IP and will therefore only be available to the Consortium.</p>
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	<p>Keywords: NET; Biofuel; Bioenergy; CCUS; CCS; Energy-Storage; BEM; TCR; P2G; PyCCS; SOTA; Experimental Study; Methodology; Cost Analysis; Cost Efficiency; Risks Impact; Market Analysis, Deliverable, SWOT, Technology Watch, Competitive Research, Market Research.</p>

Data sharing	This dataset will be stored on the institutional repository of REACH and in the project's SharePoint in M24.
Persistent identifier	N/A
File formats	N/A
File scale	100 MB (max).
Copyright & IP management	<p>According to the consortium agreement, rights to the data related to D5.1 will belong to those who were involved in their creation.</p> <p>CC-BY license is assigned for the dataset (based on secondary data originating from CC-BY sources).</p> <p>CC0 license is assigned for the metadata. This deliverable dataset, however, will not be publicly published.</p>

WP5 Task 5.2 Dataset 1/2	
Task title	Business Model Development & Business Plan
Dataset name	Business Model & Plan
Task & data manager	REACH
Other partners involved	UNIBO, FRA, LEITAT, ITHAKA, SUT, WRG
Dataset description	<p>General Description: This dataset contains collected and generated data that is needed for the development of business models and business plans for the NET-Fuels project outcomes (Key exploitable results - KERs). This dataset will support the production of the deliverable “D5.2 - NET-Fuels Business Models & Business Plan Development” in task WP5-T5.2.</p> <p>Scope of the collected Dataset: This dataset contains (i) collected information that characterizes each KER (innovative aspects, potential market, end-users, technology readiness level, competing technologies, further R&D and investment needed, means for the protection of foreground IP, other partners and stakeholders interested) as well as the most relevant market characteristics (potential market size, competitive technologies, potential end-users); (ii) data that will be generated via interactive methodologies like Business Model Canvas (BMC), Porter’s Five Forces Information, as well as SWOT and PESTEL analysis (social and economic impacts); and (iii) data received from selected potential end-users (or from available literature) as input for the defined Business Cases, based on real installations. (For the Business Plan, real business cases will be defined in relation to different technologies-configurations of the NET-Fuels overall system.)</p> <p>Main objectives: This Dataset will support T5.2 on (a) obtaining project-relevant information (defined in “Scope of the collected Dataset”); (b) making informed decisions</p>

	<p>for the elaboration of the Business Models (based on the project’s Key-Exploitable Results - KERs) and Business Plan for NET-Fuels (based on defined Business Cases) to ensure the project’s optimal exploitation.</p> <p>Main usage: This dataset will be used to develop Business Models for the KERs and a Business Plan for the overall common KER, based on selected agro-industrial business cases.</p> <p>Main Types of Data: textual, numerical, tabular, illustrations.</p> <p>Data Reuse: Existing data from task T5.1 (Market & Competitive Research), data from task T4.4 (Studying NET-Fuels impacts in the society); and from existing published high-quality peer-reviewed literature and/or from material stored in open access or proprietary sites will be reused. Since the data in this dataset is mainly project-specific, it is not of immediate use to third parties.</p>
Availability	Consortium
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Keywords: Business Model, BM, Sustainable Business Model, BM Canvas, Business Cases, Business Plan.
Data sharing	<p>The data used to prepare the Business Models and the Business Plan will be only available to the Consortium, since it will contain internal and sensitive information from the partners. The final version of the deliverable that will contain large parts of the data of this dataset will however be public.</p> <p>The collected and generated data of this dataset will be shared with the Consortium members via the NET-Fuels Share-Point repository.</p> <p>Until the data is ready to be shared in the SharePoint, it will be stored on the institutional repository of REACH.</p>
Persistent identifier	N/A
File formats	(a) Images will be stored in JPEG, PNG, TIFF or RAW formats; (b) Videos will be in average stored in mp4 or in .avi format; (c) spreadsheets (Excel format); (d) Textual files will be either stored in PDF or in open-access converted .doc formats.
File scale	10 GB (max)

WP5 Task 5.2 Dataset 2/2	
Task title	Business Model Development & Business Plan
Dataset name	NET-Fuels Business Model & Business Plan Development

Task & data manager	REACH
Other partners involved	UNIBO, FRA, LEITAT, ITHAKA, SUT, WRG
Dataset description	<p>General Description: This dataset consists of the deliverable D5.2 (Business Model and Business Plan Development), which addresses for each KER relevant aspects of its development, like IPR management strategy and the preliminary steps of the commercialization strategy for a future market uptake.</p> <p>Scope of the collected Dataset: It will report on the business models developed for the NET-Fuels KERs and on the Business Plan, both defined on the basis of the dataset WP5-T5.2-1/2. D5.2 will address results of the market analysis performed in T5.1, challenges for the market uptake, most relevant market considerations for successful implementation of the technology (potential market size, competitive technologies, potential end-users, action plans (IPR, standards)), most relevant information regarding the exploitable results, preliminary steps as commercialisation strategies and social and economic impacts.</p> <p>Main objectives & usage: to produce the Business Models and Business Plan for the NET-Fuels project, considering the KERs and appropriate Business Cases to ensure the project's optimal exploitation.</p> <p>Main Types of generated data in this Dataset are textual including illustrations and tables.</p> <p>Data Reuse: Existing data from task T5.1 (Market & Competitive Research), data from task T4.4 (Studying NET-Fuels impacts in the society), data from task T5.2-1/2 and from existing published high-quality peer-reviewed literature and/or from material stored in open access or proprietary sites will be reused. The deliverable will be useful to all researchers interested in negative biofuels initiatives as well as stakeholders in the biofuels market.</p>
Availability	Public
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	<p>Zenodo assigns metadata in accordance with Open Science rules.</p> <p>Keywords: Business Model; Business Plan; Market Uptake; Business Strategy; Business Model Development; Business Model Canvas; BMC, Value Proposition, SWOT, PESTEL, Porter's Five Forces, Business Cases.</p>
Data sharing	<p>The Deliverable data D5.2 will be made public in M46 on the open access platform Zenodo.</p> <p>Open-source tools can be used to access and use the data files in this dataset (e.g.: Libreoffice, OpenOffice, etc.).</p>
Persistent identifier	The final version of the deliverable will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	Data / File Formats: .csv, .rtf, .txt, .pdf.
File scale	100 MB (max)
Copyright & IP management	According to the consortium agreement, rights to the data related to D5.2 will belong to those who were involved in their creation. Hence, the rights belong to the NET-Fuels partners jointly.

	<p>A CC-BY license will be assigned to the deliverable and will be indicated in the metadata of the data via Zenodo.</p> <p>Metadata will receive a CC0 license.</p>
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WP5 Task 5.3 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	Regulatory assessment
Dataset name	Regulatory assessment data
Task & data manager	UNIBO
Other partners involved	FRA, LEITAT, ITHAKA, SUT, REACH, WRG (Provide information input for the regulatory framework of the project)
Dataset description	Task 5.3 assesses the regulatory framework for the project scale-up process. It defines the scope of the research (taking into account the market research analysis); compiles a database or a document in a way that can be navigated taking into account input management, processing, product quality, type of legislation, jurisdiction, subject/field of application; presenting the implementation of the project. The final output is a document (the deliverable D5.3 entitled “NET-Fuels Technology Regulatory Assessment”) and a highly informative, easy to use and simple database.
Availability	Public
Data handling standards	The Deliverable data D5.3 will be made public in M36 on the open access platform Zenodo. Open-source tools can be used to access and use the data files in this dataset.
Metadata	Keywords: market research analysis, project scale-up, regulatory framework, input management, product quality.
Data sharing	<p>Supporting data necessary to prepare the deliverable, together with the related database, will be stored on the institutional repository of UNIBO and will be shared with the partners via the project’s SharePoint.</p> <p>The deliverable D5.3 will be made public via Zenodo in M36.</p>
Persistent identifier	The final version of the deliverable will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	Deliverable will be stored as open access formats: .csv, .rtf, .txt or .pdf

File scale	From 1 MB to 1 GB
Copyright & IP management	According to the consortium agreement rights to the data will belong to those who were involved in their creation. CC-BY license is assigned for the dataset (based on secondary data originating from CC-BY sources). CCO license is assigned for the metadata.

WP5 Task 5.4 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	System scale-up for industrial scale
Dataset name	Techno-economic model
Task & data manager	FRA
Other partners involved	All Partners (participation in the definition of the selected industrial use-cases)
Dataset description	<p>This dataset consists of the output of a techno-economic model providing strategic guidance to the technical partners. This will include the update of the model based on emerging project results and the modelling of alternative process and technology scenarios. Its results will be summarized in D5.4 (Scale-up of the integrated NET-Fuels technology system for industrial level).</p> <p>The model results from the results of the operation at pilot scale (WP2 and WP3) and process and operational data provided from industrial partners. Quality will be ensured by comparison of data from pilot plant with industry.</p> <p>The purpose of this dataset is to evaluate scale-up strategies based on industrial case studies. The techno-economic model is needed to be able to provide specific guidance.</p> <p>This dataset relates to the project objective of validating the overall integrated system and approach of the project and to address the project’s Business Development for a future commercial phase, as well as Regulatory Assessment and its Potential Industrial Up-scaling.</p> <p>The new dataset from the pilot plant is required for up-scaling to industrial scale. There is no similar, existing data with a pilot plant of a similar process with similar feedstocks.</p>
Availability	Public
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	Zenodo assign metadata in accordance with the Open Science rules.

	Keywords: Anaerobic digestate, corn silage, calamity wood, prunings, pyrolysis, oxy-combustion, oxyfuel, CO ₂ , CH ₄ , BEM, Bioelectrochemical methanation, carbon capture and usage, CCU, bioenergy with carbon capture and storage, BECCS, mass balancing, energy balancing, process modelling, process simulation, Sankey diagrams, mass flows, energy flows, pilot plant, industrial scale, net zero, CAPEX, OPEX, site assessment.
Data sharing	<p>For the duration of Task 5.4 (M25-M46), data will only be stored on institutional repository of FRA and shared within the consortium on request.</p> <p>The data will be publicly shared via Zenodo after completion of the final deliverable D5.4, Scale-up of the integrated NET-Fuels technology system for industrial level in M46.</p> <p>The data will link to the project homepage, the project’s research and outputs. The data tables will have clear headers and column identifiers as is standard with data tables.</p> <p>Only a PDF viewer, internet browser for HTML and an XML editor. The rest of the data is in plaintext. No tools or documentation necessary. Data with models from specialized programs, either proprietary or open source, may be added.</p>
Persistent identifier	The final versions of the data will receive a PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	.rtf, .txt, .PDF, .csv, .md, .Rmd, .ipynb, HTML, XML, .zip
File scale	From 1 MB to 1 GB
Copyright & IP management	<p>The rights to the created data belong to FRA.</p> <p>CC-BY license will be assigned to the deliverable and will be indicated in the metadata of the data via Zenodo. Metadata will have a CC0 license.</p> <p>No IPR protection will be sought for this data set.</p>

4.6 Data Tables WP6

WP6 Task 6.1 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities
Dataset name	Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan
Task & data manager	WRG
Other partners involved	REACH
Dataset description	This dataset consists of the deliverable D6.2 (Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan) describing activities to facilitate dissemination, communication,

	and exploitation of project outputs and results to promote the key exploitable results of the project and to boost consumer acceptance and public awareness. Data is unique. The plan will provide the detail behind tasks 6.2 to 6.4. The master plan is to be reviewed and updated every 6-months during the project lifetime.
Availability	Public
Data handling standards	N/A
Metadata	Keywords: communication, dissemination, exploitation, project results, key exploitable results
Data sharing	The document will be freely available in non-editable form (pdf) via the project website and will also be uploaded to Zenodo (D6.2 - M6; D6.3 - M16; D6.4 - M36). A pdf viewer such as Adobe Acrobat will be required to view the document.
Persistent identifier	The final versions of the data will receive PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	.pdf
File scale	<15MB
Copyright & IP management	The document will be the copyright of the project consortium.

WP6 Task 6.2 Dataset 1/2	
Task title	Communication activities
Dataset name	Communication materials
Task & data manager	WRG Europe
Other partners involved	All partners (data providers)
Dataset description	Digital media will be created to communicate project updates, results, and events to targeted audiences, including the general public, the scientific community, and industry. Digital media will include newsletters, flyers, and information videos (motions graphics and infographics). Data is unique.
Availability	Public
Data handling standards	N/A
Metadata	N/A

Data sharing	Non-sensitive communication media (i.e. either protected or public domain) will be shared with target audiences including the general public, the scientific community, and industry. It will be shared via the project website, which is hosted by a secure, trusted domain handler. Moving imagery will also be shared on social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube). Data will be available until the website and social media accounts are deactivated (1 year after the project).
Persistent identifier	N/A
File formats	*.pdf, *.png, and *.mp4
File scale	Up to 300MB
Copyright & IP management	All media will be the copyright of the project and cannot be shared or used without authorization. No CC license will be applied.

WP6 Task 6.2 Dataset 2/2	
Task title	Communication activities
Dataset name	Website signup data
Task & data manager	WRG
Other partners involved	REACH, All partners (data providers)
Dataset description	People interested in receiving project newsletters or updates about the project can sign up to the website. A name and email address will be stored for subsequent mail drops. This is only for use by WRG Europe and REACH for communication purposes.
Availability	Private
Data handling standards	Data will be collected in accordance with current GDPR legislation [19].
Metadata	Keywords: communication, website, dissemination
Data sharing	The data will be shared with REACH, and with the consortium upon request, only during the period of the project lifetime.
Persistent identifier	N/A
File formats	Text file or email.
File scale	<1MB
Copyright & IP management	All data will be the copyright of the project and cannot be shared or used without authorization. No CC license will be applied.

WP6 Task 6.3 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	Dissemination of project results
Dataset name	News and blogs
Task & data manager	WRG Europe
Other partners involved	All project partners.
Dataset description	News and technical articles in conjunction with more informal blogs will be created by partners and released via the project website. This is for targeted audiences (general public, scientific community, and industry) to engage with the project and potentially create routes for exploitation. Articles/data will be unique to this project.
Availability	Public
Data handling standards	N/A
Metadata	Keywords: project results, dissemination
Data sharing	The data will be shared with any person who visits the project website. The website is hosted on a secure platform. Data will be available until the website shuts down (1 year after the project). The individual .html files will be available on company drives for 5 years after the project. A standard, modern web browser is required to access the information.
Persistent identifier	N/A
File formats	.html
File scale	<20MB
Copyright & IP management	No IP or commercially sensitive data will be shared. Any data shared will be protected by copyright and not available for free use, therefore no CC license will be applied.

WP5 Task 6.4 Dataset 1/1	
Task title	Exploitation Plan and Strategic Actions
Dataset name	Exploitation Reports (D6.3 and D6.4)
Task & data manager	REACH

Other partners involved	WRG (collaboration in task activities); All partners, UNIBO, FRA, LEITAT, ITHAKA, SUT (participate in and provide inputs for the Exploitation of the project)
Dataset description	<p>General Description: This dataset holds the contents related to Exploitation Plan and Strategic Action for the deliverables D6.3 and D6.4.</p> <p>Scope of the collected Dataset: It will report the collected information that characterizes each KER, considering the following features: Intellectual Property Right; technological-social-economic and environmental impact; technical and non-technical barriers; exploitation potential analysis and strategy; individual exploitation plans; as well cost-benefit feasibility.</p> <p>Main objectives & usage: to produce the project exploitation strategy and for elaborating an optimal Exploitation Plan for NET-Fuels, defining the Intellectual Property for the KERs, their impacts and their individual exploitation plans.</p> <p>Main Types of generated data in this Dataset are textual including illustrations and tables.</p> <p>Data Reuse: Existing data from task T5.1 (Market & Competitive Research), T5.2 (Business Model Development and Business Plan), T5.3 (Regulatory Assessment), T5.4 (System Scale-Up for Industrial Scale), T6.1 (Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Activities), and T6.3 (Dissemination of Project Results), and from existing published high-quality peer-reviewed literature and/or from material stored in open access or proprietary sites will be reused. The deliverables generated from this data set will be useful to all researchers interested in the exploitation of Net-Fuels and of negative biofuels initiatives in general, as well as stakeholders in the biofuels market.</p>
Availability	Public
Data handling standards	None.
Metadata	<p>Zenodo assigns metadata in accordance with Open Science rules.</p> <p>Keywords: Project Exploitation, Exploitation Plan, Exploitation Strategy, Intellectual Property Rights, Social-economic and environmental impact, Key Exploitable Results, Communities of Practice, Exploitation Activities.</p>
Data sharing	<p>Deliverables D6.3 and D6.4’s dataset will be shared with the Consortium members via the NET-Fuels Share-Point repository.</p> <p>Until the generated data is ready to be shared in the Share-Point Repository, REACH will be working on its cloud server.</p> <p>The Deliverables’ data will be made public in Months M16 (D6.3) and M36 (D6.4) on the open access platform Zenodo.</p> <p>Open-source tools can be used to access and use the data files in this dataset (e.g.: Libreoffice, OpenOffice, etc.).</p>
Persistent identifier	The final versions of the data will receive PID from Zenodo (DOI).
File formats	Data / File Formats: .csv, .rtf, .txt, .pdf.

File scale	100 MB (max)
Copyright & IP management	<p>The rights to D6.3 and D6.4 belong to the partners jointly.</p> <p>A CC-BY license will be assigned to the deliverables and will be indicated in the metadata of the data via Zenodo. Metadata will have a CC0 license.</p>

5 Conclusion

This 3rd Version of the Data Management Plan (D1.2 – DMP V3.0) updates and replaces the last published version of the Data Management Plan (D1.2 - DMP V2.0), which in turns updated the original NET-Fuels DMP (D1.2 - DMP V1.0) [20]. This DMP outlines the handling of the NET-Fuels project data, providing orientation to the project partners, as well as to third parties, such as researchers, policy-makers and other stakeholders, regarding the content, validity and accessibility of the project's data and other outputs. This document also stated the data management strategy for the NET-Fuels project, which was co-created by involving all partners under the lead of partner REACH within WP1-T1.3.

The Data Management Plan versions for the NET-Fuels project are planned to be updated for every reporting period (RP) and possibly, also in between the reports in case major developments and changes are made to the project implementation that affect the project's data management.

For every RP a new version of this DMP is planned to be released. In total there will be four versions of this DMP. The versions of the DMP will reflect the changes to the data tables made in the following periods:

- **Version 1:** (D1.2 – DMP V1.0), M1-M6, published in April 2023.
- **Version 2:** (D1.2 – DMP V2.0), M7-M18, released in M20 (June 2024).
- **Version 3:** (D1.2 – DMP V3.0), M19-36, prepared in M38 (December 2025, current version).
- **Version 4:** (D1.2 – DMP V4.0), M37-48, to be released in M48 (October 2026).

The current document “NET-Fuels Data Management Plan” (D1.2 – DMP V3.0), by [Horizon Europe Project "NET-Fuels"](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC-BY\)](#), and will be publicly available on the project's Zenodo Community (https://zenodo.org/communities/net_fuels_horizon_europe_project/).

6 References

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3. European Commission. Horizon Europe Programme Guide V2.0 – 11.04.2022, https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf.
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7. OpenAire Guide for Researchers: How to comply with Horizon Europe mandate for Research Data Management. <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-comply-with-horizon-europe-mandate-for-rdm>.
8. CC Creative Commons. Creative Commons Public Licenses: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>
9. Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management - Extended Edition, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915862>.
10. European Commission. Ethics and Data Protection Decision Tree: <https://ec.europa.eu/assets/rtd/ethics-data-protection-decision-tree/index.html>
11. European Commission. Horizon Europe Template for the Data Management Plan: <https://enspire.science/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Horizon-Europe-Data-Management-Plan-Template.pdf>
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13. Axiom Data Science. Data Management Best Practices: <https://www.axiomdatascience.com/best-practices/index.html#>
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15. Science Europe (2019). Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management from. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.4915861, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915861> https://scienceeurope.org/media/4brkxe5/se_rdm_practical_guide_extended_final.pdf.
16. Horizon Europe Project NET-Fuels Nr.: 101083780 – Deliverable D6.2: NET-Fuels Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan V1.0, 30/04/2023. (Publication available in Zenodo: [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7987173](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7987173)).
17. Horizon Europe Project NET-Fuels Nr.: 101083780 – Deliverable D6.3: 1st Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Report, covering the period of 30/04/2023 to 29/02/2024 (M6-M16). (Publication available in Zenodo: DOI [10.5281/zenodo.11176109](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11176109)).

18. Horizon Europe Project NET-Fuels - Grant Agreement Number: 101083780, Zenodo Community: https://zenodo.org/communities/net_fuels_horizon_europe_project/.
19. GDPR: The General Data Protection Regulation [Regulation \(EU\) 2016/679](#) & The Data Protection Law Enforcement Directive [Directive \(EU\) 2016/680](#) . [EU GDPR legislation](#).
20. Horizon Europe Project NET-Fuels Nr.: 101083780 – Deliverable D1.2: NET-Fuels Data Management Plan (DMP) V1.0, 30/04/2023, updated as V2.0 on June 2024 (Publication available in Zenodo: DOI [10.5281/zenodo.7968001](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7968001)).

7 Annex

7.1 Guidelines for Filling out the Data Tables

NET- Fuels

INCREASING BIOMASS CONVERSION EFFICIENCY TO CARBON-NEGATIVE SUSTAINABLE BIOFUELS BY COMBINATION OF THERMOCHEMICAL AND BIO-ELECTROCHEMICAL PROCESSES

HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-09 | GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER: 101083780

WP1 – Management, Coordination & Risk Management

Task T1.3 – Data Management

Guidelines for the Data Management Table

The purpose of the DMP is to **plan and document your research and work methodologies** and to ensure that the data is handled in the best possible way as well as **in accordance with the Open Science¹⁶ requirements of the EC**.

For **every WP task**, please fill out the table exemplified below for all research datasets, as well as for all datasets pertaining to other outputs that result from your task (e.g.: software, workflows, protocols, prototypes, presentations, posters etc.). It may be that a task will generate more than one type of dataset. In that case, please make a copy of the table within your WP-Task table file, for each type of dataset and number them accordingly (e.g.: Dataset X/X: 1/3, 2/3, 3/3, etc.).

Research data handling needs to conform to Open Science requirements (*‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’*). Consult the *Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management* from “Science Europe”¹⁷ and the *HE Programme Guide*¹⁸ for detailed guidance on the requirements.

Note that the rules on Open Science are **mandatory for research data**, while they are only recommended for all other data. Nevertheless, it is strongly suggested to conform as much as possible to the Open Science rules also in the latter case whenever that is reasonable.

Please be as specific as possible when you fill out the table and justify thoroughly when Open Science requirements cannot be conformed to.

For each WP-Task, you find a form in the SharePoint Folder of WP1-T1.3 that needs to be completed and then uploaded again back to the same place. The file name convention adopted is: WP (Z) and task (Y.Y) in the following format: **DM-WPZ-TY.Y-v01.docx**.

¹⁶ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915862>

¹⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf, esp pp 37ff.

7.2 Data Table Template

Data Management Table:

WPY Task Y.Y Dataset X/X ¹⁹	
Task title	<i>Title of the task as it is mentioned in the Gantt chart.</i>
Dataset name	<i>Choose a name for the dataset that facilitates its identification.</i>
Task & data manager	<i>Name of task leader (institution) and name of the individual responsible for the data management of the task.</i>
Other partners involved	<i>Name of other partner institutions working on the task.</i>
Dataset description	<i>Describe the data and its purpose, origin and nature in relation to project objectives, quality assurance processes applied in its creation/generation, to whom it is useful outside the project. State whether there is similar, already existing data; justify if reuse of existing data has been discarded.</i>
Availability	<i>Choose “Private”, “Consortium” or “Public”.</i>
Data handling standards	<i>If any, indicate if there are existing disciplinary standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing.</i>
Metadata	<i>If any, indicate whether there are disciplinary standards for assigning metadata. If there are none, indicate how metadata will be created, whether they are interoperable and how long it will be available. Indicate which keywords (beside the general project-specific keywords) will be assigned to make your data findable.</i>
Data sharing	<i>Indicate whether and with whom the data will be shared, and on which (trusted) repository. Indicate when and until when the data will be shared. If any, state existence of embargo period (permissible only in case of future commercial exploitation, sensitivity of data etc.). State the software or tools necessary for reuse and validation of the data. Explain whether/where/what kind of data documentation there will be to ensure validation of the data analysis to persons outside the project.</i>
Persistent identifier	<i>Indicate whether a persistent identifier will be assigned and which kind (e.g.: DOI).</i>
File formats	<i>Indicate file formats of the data reused and/or generated.</i>
File scale	<i>Indicate the expected size of the data reused and/or generated.</i>

¹⁹ This table was created using as guidance the Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management from “Science Europe”, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915862>; the Horizon Europe DMP template; Data Management Plan of Horizon 2020 Project “BioSFerA”, Grant agreement ID: 884208, Project DOI: 10.3030/884208, pp 13-14.

Archiving and preservation	<i>[P, L, M, C] Outline the procedure for long-term preservation (P), length of preservation (L), prevention measures for data loss (data recovery) (M), and make an estimation of costs and how those will be covered (C).</i>
Copyright & IP management	<i>Indicate who will have the rights to the data created/collected and which/how Creative Commons (CC) license²⁰ will be assigned to both data and metadata (in most cases only CC0 or CC-BY are permitted). If you are reusing data that belongs to someone else, indicate whether you have permission or license to use and store it in a repository.</i>
Ethical issues management	<i>State if there are potential ethical or legal issues connected with data collection or data sharing, e.g.: sensitive data, see especially the EU Regulation 2016/679 GDPR.²¹</i>
Additional data management procedures	<i>Indicate with links if you are following other data management procedures than those of Horizon Europe (e.g.: institutional procedures).</i>

²⁰ <https://creativecommons.org/about/cclicenses/>

²¹ <https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/eu-legislation/gdpr/>; <https://ec.europa.eu/assets/rtd/ethics-data-protection-decision-tree/index.html>